

NOTES

Inorganic Coordination Complexes. Part II. Preparation and Structural Studies on Dihalogenobis (N-methylacetamide) Zinc(II)

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MIZUSHIMA and Schimanouchi¹ have extensively studied the infrared spectrum of N-methylacetamide. Several coordination complexes of N-methylacetamide in which the metal ion is either coordinated through oxygen or through the substituted amide nitrogen have been reported²⁻⁴. The present manuscript deals with the preliminary report of the complexes of zinc halides with N-methylacetamide together with physico-chemical characterisation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. A.R grade or E. Mercks G. R. grade. The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of zinc halides and excess of N-methylacetamide solution in 95 percent ethanol for one hour on steam bath with stirring. Crystalline complexes obtained on cooling were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether successively and dried in vacuum over calcium chloride.

Zinc and halides were determined gravimetrically as zinc-pyridine thiocyanate and silver halide respectively⁵. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated microanalytically.

Conductivity and molecular weight were determined in nitrobenzene. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer (model 621) in 4000-200 cm^{-1} region. Solid state electronic spectra were obtained on Cary-14 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The results of the investigation have been recorded in Tables 1 and 2 with pertinent data.

Disappearance of N-H out of plane bending vibration of N-methylacetamide in its complexes with zinc halides evidently indicates the coordination through substituted amide nitrogen⁶. Since N-methylacetamide is highly associated through hydrogen bonding in liquid state⁷⁻⁹, the N-H bond may become weaker in the complexes and so resulted in an increase in its frequency rather than lowered.

Zn-N, Zn-X (X=Cl, Br and I) stretching modes of^{10,11} molar conductance and normal absolute values of molecular weight are in good agreement with the general formula $[\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_2)_2 \times 2]^\circ$ for these complexes. Further, these complexes are supposed to have tetrahedral structure as a result of Sp^3 -hybridisation.

The spectra of dihalogeno bis(N-methylacetamide) zinc(II) showed only one band at 24500 cm^{-1} . Since no d-d transition is expected for Zn^{2+} , as it has d^{10} configuration, this band may be assigned as charge transfer band.

TABLE I—RESULTS OF ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Analysis %					Molar conductance (mhos)	Molecular weight	Electronic spectral band (cm^{-1})
			Zn	C	H	N	X			
1.	$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$	White	22.95 (23.06)	25.50 (25.54)	4.84 (4.96)	9.80 (9.93)	25.00 (25.16)	0.42	282.05 (283.33)	24500
2.	$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_2)_2\text{Br}_2$	White	17.45 (17.61)	19.50 (19.41)	3.28 (3.77)	7.20 (7.54)	43.00 (42.84)	0.24	368.64 (371.25)	24500
3.	$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_2)_2\text{I}_2$	Greyish White	13.88 (14.05)	15.36 (15.49)	2.98 (3.01)	6.00 (6.02)	54.06 (54.55)	0.30	463.86 (465.23)	24500

Calculated values are given in parenthesis.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECIAL DATA (cm⁻¹)

CH ₃ CONHCH ₃ (liquid)	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ Br ₂	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ I ₂	Assignment
3300s	3890	3886	3876	N-H stretching vibration (bonded)
3110s	2940s	2940w	2946m	C-H stretching vibration (sym)
2940s				
2890sh	2715w	2712w	2710w	
2720w				
1653s	1660	1666s	1666s	Amide I
1567s	1530s	1524s	1505s	Amide II
1445m	1450m	1450m	1462s	CH ₃ N deformation vibration
1413s	1422m	1426m	1430m	(sym)
1373s	1380s	1385s	1386s	CH ₃ C deformation (sym)
1299s	1310s	1322s	1318s	Amide III
1159s	1162m	1160m	1160m	CH ₃ N rocking vibration
1096m	1095w	1096m	1098m	CH ₃ -N, CH ₃ -C stretching vibration
1040m	1040m	1045m	1046m	CH ₃ C rocking
937m	950w		945m	
881m	885w	890w	892w	N-H-out of plane bending vibration CH ₃ -C rocking
725m				
	236m	248m	240m	M-N mode
	326s	305s	300s	
	298m	270m	280m	M-X vibration

s=Strong, m=medium, w=weak, sh=shoulder,
 sym=symmetric, Amide I=(C=O) stretching vibration
 Amide II=N-H deformation vibration or C-H stretching vibration,
 Amide III=O-C-N and N-H vibrations, X-Cl, Br, I.

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Determination of Gold and Copper with *p*-(2-Mercaptopropionamido)benzoic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent

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GOLD is normally determined by reduction to the metallic state¹. Complex-forming organic precipitants are very few indeed. *p*-(2-Mercaptopropionamido)benzoic acid², which was introduced as a valuable reagent for the determination of silver and mercury, has been observed to complex Au(I) which is precipitated quantitatively at pH 0.5 to 3.5. Cu(II), too, is precipitated quantitatively at pH 2.0 to 4.8, however, gold can be separated from Cu(II) by sequestering the latter with EDTA. Au(III) is reduced to Au(I) before complexation. The reagent offers the advantages of adequate solubility in aqueous medium, ease of preparation and selectivity of reaction.

Determination of Au(I) and Cu(II) :

Twenty ml of the solution (0.2%, m/V, of gold solution and 0.1%, m/V, of copper solution were used) of the cation to be estimated is taken in a